

Growth and Morphological Characterisation in Two Accessions of Sesame Plant

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Abstract

Sesamum indicum is a warm-season annual crop that is herbaceous, erected with branches exhibiting considerable variations in growth habit, seed traits, and flower characteristics. This study evaluates two accessions (white and black varieties) through morphological and germinability comparative analysis. The heights of the plant and leaf size were measured using a ruler while the stem girth was determined using vernier caliper. Germinability potential was evaluated by presoaking 100 seeds from each variety in 5% sodium hypochlorite for 15 min., rinsed with distilled water, and placed under moist conditions. Results showed the white sesame variety had higher plant height (41.98 cm), stem girth (3.23 cm), and leaf size (13.89 cm²) than the black variety (34.30 cm, 2.68 cm, and 7.47 cm², respectively). In contrast, the black variety produced more leaves (105.06) and branches (10.41). Significant variations were observed in all morphological traits except the stem girth. Reproductive performance was superior in the white accession, which showed higher numbers of flowers (7.18) and capsules (17.44), along with greater 100-seed (1.67 g) and 1000 seed weights (16.67 g); these traits were not observed in the black variety. Microscopic analysis revealed that trichomes were almost sevenfold higher in the white variety, whereas stomata size was over 1.5-fold greater in the black variety. Germinability analysis indicated that 98 of 100 seeds (98%) germinated in the white variety, compared to 86 of 100 seeds (86%) in the black variety. The white sesame accession therefore displayed clear superiority in morphological performance and germination ability, demonstrating its potential in genetic improvement, seed quality enhancement, and sustainable sesame crop production relevant in the field of Biotechnology.

Keywords: Accessions of Sesame Plant, Characterization, Growth, Morphology

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Introduction

Sesamum indicum L. is an annual plant of important oilseed crop cultivated primarily for its seeds, which contained about 50% oil. The crop is widely considered to have originated from Africa, particularly the West African region, from where it spreads through western Asia to India, China, and Japan and from there to other parts of the world (Dia, and Gwandi, 2015). It was domesticated over 3,000 years ago; evidence of early sesame production has been found dating back to 1600 B.C in the Tigris and Euphrates valleys (AGMRC, 2022). It is a member of the family *Pedaliacea* (Gwandi et al., 2021). Main areas of cultivation in Nigeria are found to be between latitudes 60° and 100° N in the guinea and Sudan savannah zones including large portions of present day Jigawa, Benue, Kwara, Kogi, Nasarawa, and Niger States (House, 2018). Sesame has relatively higher seed oil content ranging from 40 % to 60 % when compared to oilseed crops like soybean (~20 %), rapeseed (~40 %), sunflower (~45 %), and groundnut (45–56 %) (Teklu et al., 2022). The oil extracted from sesame seed consists both saturated and unsaturated fatty acids representing about 15 % and 85 %, respectively (Teklu et al., 2022). The saturated fatty acid includes stearic acid and palmitic acid, whereas the unsaturated ones includes oleic acid and linoleic acid (Dossa et al., 2018; Anastasi et al., 2017). The genus *Sesamum* comprises of about 35 recognized species of which *S. indicum* L. is the most widely cultivated specie (Parsaeian et al., 2020). Various parts of sesame have been widely used around the globe for their ethno medicinal values (Mili et al., 2021). The aerial parts are used in managing impotence, the leaves serves as anti-malaria, treatment of mouth inflammation, diabetes and diarrhea, while the seed and paste has been used for managing ailments of wounds and burns, cholera, respiratory infections. In addition, the fruits have been used as a laxative, whereas the roots are used for treating asthma and hair growth (Mili et al., 2021).

Over time, plants have been cultivated for several reasons of which high yield trait is prominent. Production of sesame is affected by several factors, of which understanding its growth and morphological characteristics would give an insight on the improvement of the

sesame production. Therefore, this research focuses on evaluating key growth and morphological characteristics with the aim of enhancing sesame productivity and identifying accessions with desirable traits for potential biotechnological applications such as genetic improvement, seed quality enhancement, and sustainable crop development.

Study Area

The research was performed at the School Garden, Biological Sciences, Federal University of Kashere, Gombe State, Nigeria (latitude 10°16'N - 10°18'N, longitude 11°8'E - 11°12'E) (Kolawole et al., 2018).

Experimental Design

A complete randomized block design was utilized using five replicates for each treatment, which included five colchicine concentrations (0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, and 0.4 % w/v) along with a control. The study duration was 20 weeks based on the duration employed by Kumari (2024).

Plant Material

Two accessions of *Sesamum indicum* (white and black varieties) were identified and sourced from experts in the biological garden of Federal University of Kashere, Gombe State and used for the research work.

Morphological Characterisation

Morphological parameters such as plant height, leaf number, leaf size, stem girth, branch number, flower count, and capsule number were measured. The heights of the plant and leaf size were measured with ruler, whereas stem girth was measured using vernier caliper. The area of the leaves was obtained with the formula $\text{Area} = L \times B \times 0.72$, where L = length, B = maximum width and 0.72 is a constant (Hussain et al., 2023).

Seed Germinability test

One hundred seeds from each variety were presoaked in 5 % sodium hypochlorite for 15 minutes, followed by thorough rinse with water. Germinability was assessed by placing the seeds in moist conditions and calculating the percentage of germinated seeds using the formula: {Germinability (%) = (Number of

germinated seeds / Total number of seeds) × 100} Adapted from Lavallee et al., (2021); Mangena and Mokwala, (2019); Zhang et al., (2013); Alhammad et al., (2023).

Cultural Practices

Plants were watered daily and treated with poultry manure before planting. Weeding was conducted regularly.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis of the data was performed with one-way ANOVA and Bonferroni tests was used for notable differences using post-hoc at $P \leq 0.05$ with IBM SPSS version 21.0, IBM Corp, 2012.

Results and Discussions

Results

Morphological parameters

Measurements are summarized in Table 1. The white accession had a mean plant height of 41.98 ± 2.80 cm, mean leaf area 13.89 ± 0.88 cm², and stem girth 3.23 ± 0.73 cm. The black accession had mean plant height 34.30 ± 1.80 cm, mean leaf area 7.47 ± 0.10 cm², and stem girth 2.68 ± 0.26 cm. The mean number of leaves per plant was 68.60 ± 7.90 for the white accession and 105.06 ± 2.96 for the black accession. Mean branch number was 4.83 ± 0.50 (white) and 10.41 ± 1.37 (black). One-way ANOVA indicated statistically significant differences between accessions ($p \leq 0.05$) for number of branches, leaf area, plant height, and number of leaves, but stem girth did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) as indicated at Table 1 (one).

Table 1: Morphological parameters evaluated on *Sesamum indicum* [Mean \pm Standard Error]

Accessions of Sesame	Height of Plant (cm)	Number of Leaves	Size of Leaves (cm ²)	Stem Girth (cm)	Number of Branches
White variety	$41.98 \pm 2.80^*$	$68.60 \pm 7.90^*$	$13.89 \pm 0.88^*$	3.23 ± 0.73^{Ns}	$4.83 \pm 0.50^*$
Black variety	$34.30 \pm 1.80^*$	$105.06 \pm 2.96^*$	$7.47 \pm 0.10^*$	2.68 ± 0.26^{Ns}	$10.41 \pm 1.37^*$

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$, Ns: Not significant

Assessment of Reproductive parameters

Reproductive measurements for the white accession were: mean number of flowers 7.18 ± 1.11 , mean number of capsules 17.44 ± 3.43 , 100-seed weight 1.67 ± 0.14 g, and 1000-seed weight 16.67 ± 1.40 g. The black accession

recorded 0.00 ± 0.00 for flowers, capsules, and seed weight measures under the experimental conditions. The observed differences in reproductive parameters between accessions were observed significant statistically ($p \leq 0.05$) as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Reproductive parameters evaluated on *Sesamum indicum*

Accessions of Sesame	Number of Flowers	Number of Capsules	100 seed weight (g)	1000 seed weight (g)
White variety diploid	$7.18 \pm 1.11^*$	$17.44 \pm 3.43^*$	$1.67 \pm 0.14^*$	$16.67 \pm 1.40^*$

Black variety diploid	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
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Ns: Not significant down a column, *Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Analysis of Trichome for white and black Sesame varieties

The white accession averaged 41.90 ± 4.85 trichomes per microscopic field; the black

accession averaged 6.60 ± 6.02 trichomes per field. Trichome count varied considerably between accessions at $p \leq 0.05$. Trichome size (μ^2) and trichome density didn't significantly differ between accessions at $p > 0.05$ as depicted in Table 3.

Table 3: Trichome analysis for white and black Sesame varieties

Peltate hair trichome studies	Number of Trichomes per view	Trichome size (μ^2)	Trichome density
White variety diploid			
Trichomes	$41.90 \pm 4.85^*$	2302.70 ± 284.16^{NS}	0.12 ± 0.13^{NS}
Black variety diploid			
Trichomes	$6.60 \pm 6.02^*$	2352.50 ± 134.89^{NS}	0.18 ± 0.01^{NS}

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$, Ns: Not significant down a column

Stomata evaluation from white and black sesame variety

Stomatal observations showed the white accession had mean stomatal count 9.63 ± 0.91 per field and stomatal size $23.35 \pm 1.90 \mu^2$; the

black accession had mean stomatal count 6.50 ± 0.54 and stomatal size $35.85 \pm 3.62 \mu^2$. Number of stomata per field and stomatal size differed significantly between accessions ($p \leq 0.05$), while stomatal density did not at $p > 0.05$ as shown in Table four (4).

Table 4: Evaluation of Stomata from white and black sesame variety

Accessions	Number of stomata per microscopic view	Stomata size (μ^2)	Stomata density
White variety			
Stomata	$9.63 \pm 0.91^*$	$23.35 \pm 1.90^*$	0.03 ± 0.00^{NS}
Black variety			
Stomata	$6.50 \pm 0.54^*$	$35.85 \pm 3.62^*$	0.02 ± 0.00^{NS}

Ns: Not significant down a column, *Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Germinability analysis of the white and black sesame variety

Germination onset occurred at day 4 for the white accession and day 5 for the black accession. Final germination percentages were

98% (white; 98/100) and 86% (black; 86/100). According to the statistical analysis presented, germinability percentage variations were not significant statistically at $p > 0.05$ as depicted in Table five (5).

Table 5: Germinability of Seeds in Petri dish

Sesame type	Number of days	Frequency	Percentage germinability (%)
White variety	4.00±0.00 ^{Ns}	98.00±0.00 ^{Ns}	98.00±0.00 ^{Ns}
Black variety	5.00±0.00 ^{Ns}	86.00±0.00 ^{Ns}	86.00±0.00 ^{Ns}

Ns: Not significant

Discussion

This study compared two accessions of *Sesamum indicum* (white and black) with respect to their vegetative, reproductive and epidermal traits. The white accession exhibit superior plant height, larger leaf area and measurable reproductive output (flowers, capsules, and seed weights) as relatively compared with the black accession under the conditions tested. Conversely, the black accession recorded higher leaf counts and branch numbers.

The greater plant height and leaf area of the white accession indicates a tendency towards higher above-ground biomass, which commonly correlates with greater photosynthetic capacity and yield potential. The higher number of leaves and branches observed in the black accession may reflect a different growth pattern (more compact or branching) rather than higher biomass per axis; such structural differences can influence harvest index and crop management decisions. From a biotechnological and breeding perspective, these contrasting growth patterns provide useful phenotypic markers for selection depending on target production goals.

Regarding the reproductive performance, only the white accession produced measurable flowers, capsules and seed weights in this trial. The complete absence of reproductive structures in the black accession under the experimental conditions may be attributed to environmental factors (temperature, photoperiod), seed physiological status, or genetic differences in

phenology. Similar variability in reproductive traits among sesame accessions has been reported in the literature (like; Teklu et al., 2022; Dossa et al., 2018), indicating that genotype X environment interactions play a critical role in sesame productivity. This reproductive advantage further positioned the white accession as a valuable candidate for genetic improvement and seed yield optimization research.

Epidermal features (trichomes and stomata) revealed that the white accession distinctly had more trichomes per microscopic field than the black accession, while the black accession presented larger stomatal size. Trichome abundance can influence pest resistance and microclimate at the leaf surface, whereas stomatal size impacts gas exchange and transpiration. The observed combination, more trichomes but smaller stomata in the white accession may partly explain its superior morphological and reproductive performance. However, trichome size and density were not statistically different, suggesting that number rather than size/density constitutes the more variable epidermal trait between these accessions.

Germinability result highlights white accession exhibited higher germination percentage (98%) compared to the black accession (86%), although the difference was not statistically significant in this dataset. Germination timing (white = day 4, black = day 5) suggests marginally faster emergence for the white accession under tested conditions. Seed quality,

storage conditions, and minor differences in seed physiology could explain these results (Lavallee et al., 2021; Shahbazi et al., 2022).

In recommendations, the absence of reproductive data for the black accession is a key limitation; further trials across seasons and locations are recommended to determine whether this result is consistent. Future work should also include biomass harvests, yield per plant, and biochemical profiling of seeds. Additionally, controlled experiments to examine the effect of colchicine concentrations (it was listed in Experimental Design) on morphological traits should be reported separately if applied.

The combined vegetative and reproductive data collectively indicate that the white accession is a promising candidate for cultivation and breeding programs aimed at seed yield, while the black accession's leaf and branching architecture may still possess niche agronomic value where alternative plant habits are required. Integrating multi-location and multi-season evaluations will strengthen varietal recommendations and support future biotechnological exploitation of desirable traits.

Conclusion

Morphological characterization of sesame accessions was performed by determining the parameters like size of leaves, number of leaves, plant height, number of branches, and stem Girth. Plant height, stem girth, and size of leaves were observed higher in the white sesame variety, conversely other parameters like number of branches and number of leaves in the black sesame variety have higher values as recorded. There is a significant differences in all the morphological parameters evaluated between both the sesame accessions at $p \leq 0.05$, except stem girth which did not show significant difference statistically. Also, the white

variety of the sesame accession had shown a good reproductive capacity, but there was no reproductive parameter observed from the black variety. The number of Trichomes per view in the white sesame variety was also discovered higher than the black variety by about 7 folds. These clearly indicated that the white sesame variety had shown good attributes of seed and could be optimally utilized for cultivation purposes.

The demonstrated superiority of the white accession in growth performance, reproductive capacity, and seed germination highlights its potential as a candidate genotype for breeding, genetic enhancement, and sustainable sesame production research programs in the field of Biotechnology. Therefore, the white sesame variety can be considered a more promising accession for cultivation and future improvement efforts, despite multi-environment validation is recommended.

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